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**BRONCHOGENIC CYST OF THE FILUM TERMINALE -CORRELATION OF
PREOPERATIVE MRI WITH INTRAOPERATIVE ULTRASOUND AND HISTOPATHOLOGY
CASE REPORT**

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Abstract. The aim of our study was to share our experience by comparing preoperative MRI with intraoperative ultrasound and postoperative histopathology in a very rare disease. A 24-year-old patient presented to our hospital with lower back pain radiating to the right leg, accompanied by numbness in the same region, bladder and bowel dysfunction, erectile problems, and sexual disability. MRI with contrast of the spinal cord was performed, revealing a mass. The lesion was intradural at the Th12–L1 level, but it was difficult to determine whether it was intramedullary. A surgical decision was made. Th12–L1 laminectomy was performed. Using intraoperative neuromonitoring and intraoperative ultrasound, the level of the lesion was precisely assessed. After opening the meningeal layer, the tumor was visualized at the end of the conus medullaris. With microvascular surgical technique, the tumor was removed, achieving gross total resection. Histologically, the patient was diagnosed with a bronchogenic cyst.

The patient was discharged from the hospital without neurological complications.

Postoperatively, we monitored the patient systematically, and no recurrence was observed at 18-month follow-up.

With this study, we want to emphasize that although these benign tumors are mostly located at upper levels of the spinal cord, bronchogenic cysts can also appear at the end of the conus, before the cauda equina. Correlation of preoperative MRI with intraoperative ultrasound provides very reliable results. With accurate histological diagnosis, patients can have a long tumor-free life.

Keywords: Bronchogenic Cyst, MRI correlation with IOUS, Spinal Cord Tumor, Filum Terminale.

ტერმინალური ძაფის ბრონქოგენული კისტა - ოპერაციამდელი მაგნიტურ-
რეზონანსული ტომოგრაფიის კორელაცია ინტრაოპერაციულ ულტრაბგერით
გამოკვლევასთან და ჰისტოპათოლოგიასთან.

აბსტრაქტი. ჩვენი კვლევის მიზანი იყო საკუთარი კლინიკური გამოცდილების გაზიარება ძალიან იშვიათი დაავადების შესახებ, პრეოპერაციული მაგნიტურ-რეზონანსული ტომოგრაფიის (MRI) მონაცემების შედარება ინტრაოპერაციულ ულტრაბგერასთან და პოსტოპერაციული ჰისტოპათოლოგიური კვლევის შედეგებთან. 24 წლის პაციენტმა მომართა კლინიკას ჩივილებით: წელის ტკივილი, რომელიც გადაეცემოდა მარჯვენა ფეხში, დაბუჟება ამავე კიდურში, შარდვისა და კუჭის მოქმედების მოშლა და სექსუალური დისფუნქცია. ჩატარებულ იქნა ზურგის ტვინის MRT კვლევა კონტრასტით, გამოვლინდა ინტრადურული მოცულობითი წარმონაქმნი Th12–L1 დონეზე; თუმცა რთული იყო იმის დადგენა, იყო თუ არა წარმონაქმნი ინტრამედულური. დაიგეგმა ქირურგიული ჩარევა. ჩატარდა Th12–L1 ლამინექტომია. ინტრაოპერაციული ნეირომონიტორინგისა და ულტრაბგერის გამოყენებით დაზუსტდა წარმონაქმნის ზუსტი ლოკალიზაცია. მაგარი გარსის გახსნის შემდეგ კონუსის კაუდალურად ნანახი იქნა სიმსივნე. მიკროქირურგიული ტექნიკის გამოყენებით განხორციელდა მისი სრული ამოკვეთა. ჰისტოლოგიურად დიაგნოსტირებულ იქნა, ბრონქოგენური კისტა. პაციენტი გაეწერა კლინიკადან ნევროლოგიური დეფიციტის გარეშე. პოსტოპერაციული კონტროლის შედეგად 18-თვის განმავლობაში სიმსივნის რეციდივი არ აღინიშნება.

მიუხედავად იმისა, რომ ამ ტიპის კეთილთვისებიანი წარმონაქმნები უმეტესად ზურგის ტვინის კრანიალურად გვხვდება, ბრონქოგენული კისტები შესაძლოა მდებარეობდეს ზურგის ტვინის კონუსისა და საბოლოო ძაფის დონეზე. ოპერაციამდელი MRT–ს შედეგების კორელაცია ინტრაოპერაციულ ულტრაბგერასთან ზუსტი დიაგნოსტირებისა და მინიმალინვაზიურად სიმსივნის ამოკვეთის საშუალებას იძლევა.

საკვანძო სიტყვები: ბრონქოგენული კისტა, MRI-ის კორელაცია IOUS-თან, ზურგის ტვინის სიმსივნე, ტერმინალური ძაფი.

Introduction. Intradural extramedullary bronchogenic cyst is an extremely rare congenital malformation. It is a type of endodermal cyst that occurs due to abnormal development of the embryonic period. A lesion is termed a bronchogenic cyst if the endodermal lining is predominated with respiratory tract epithelium, with pseudo stratified ciliated columnar epithelia that is normally found in the tracheobronchial tract. These cysts are therefore remnants of primitive foregut from which the respiratory system originates [3]. Bronchogenic cysts are mostly found in the lung or mediastinum but rarely occur in cutaneous and subcutaneous tissues, the pericardium, the diaphragm, the abdomen, and the spinal cord. Intraspinal BCs are exceedingly rare, with only 29 surgically treated cases reported in the literature [1,4,5].

Intraspinal bronchogenic cysts are usually present with axial pain, radicular pain, or signs of spinal cord compression, where they require surgical intervention. They are mostly located in the cervical spine in 51% of cases, followed by the lumbar spine in 17% in the intradural extramedullary compartment [2].

In the recent medical literature, we found only 2 cases of resection of bronchogenic cyst of the filum terminale, published by Kandula V et al in 2016 [3] and Ali M Sumayli et al in 2025 [5]. In this regard, our goal is to document our own very rare case.

Case Presentation

A 24-year-old patient presented to our hospital with lower back pain radiating to the right leg, accompanied by numbness in the same region, bladder and bowel dysfunction, erectile problems, and sexual disability.

MRI findings

MRI with contrast of the spinal cord was performed, revealing a mass. The lesion was intradural at the Th12–L1 level, but it was difficult to determine whether it was intramedullary. At the Th12/L1 vertebral level, within the spinal canal and predominantly along the dorsal aspect, there is a partially formed 1,5cm in diameter lesion demonstrating heterogeneous T2 hyperintensity with fluid-like signal characteristics (Figures 1-2).

Figure 1-2: Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the lumbar spine with contrast, showing 1,5 cm diameter intradural tumor.

Surgical procedure

A surgical decision was made. Th12–L1 laminectomy was performed. Using intraoperative neuromonitoring and intraoperative ultrasound, the level of the lesion was precisely assessed. After opening the meningeal layer, the tumor was visualized at the end of the conus medullaris. With microvascular surgical technique, the tumor was removed, achieving gross total resection.

Histopathology

Histopathological examination revealed a connective tissue wall of a cyst lined with respiratory pseudostratified epithelium, mucus-producing glands, and adjacent fatty tissue. Immunohistochemical examination revealed CK6 expression on the lining epithelium (Figures 3-6). CK20 was negative. P63 was positive on basal cells. Ki67 (MIB1+) - in a single cell. A diagnosis of bronchogenic cyst was made.

Figure 3-4: Low power magnification histopathology slide showing the cyst wall lined by respiratory (bronchiolar type) epithelium with underlying fibrous tissue (H&E stain).

Figure 5: High magnification histopathology slide showing ciliated pseudostratified columnar cells with scattered goblet cells (H&E stain).

Figure 6: High magnification histopathology slide showing the cyst wall lined by respiratory epithelium with underlying fibrous tissue containing seromucinous glands (H&E stain).

Postoperative course

The patient was discharged from the hospital without neurological complications.

Postoperatively, we monitored the patient systematically, and no recurrence was observed at 18-month follow-up.

Discussion

Intradural extramedullary lesions represent a wide range of different entities. These include primary (schwannoma, meningioma, myxopapillary ependymoma in conus, epidermoid) and secondary (metastases, lymphoma etc.) tumors and tumor-like lesions. A very rare pathology is intraspinal bronchogenic cyst. The mechanism of its development has not been established. Endodermal cysts are anatomical malformations that originate from congenital remnants of the primitive foregut as a result of the abnormal partitioning of the presumptive endoderm and the embryonic notochordal plate during day 21 of embryogenesis. A bronchogenic cyst refers to an endodermal cyst that is mainly lined with goblet cells, columnar epithelium cells, and pseudostratified ciliated epithelial cells [4]. Intraspinal bronchogenic cyst is typically intradural extramedullary lesions, most located at the cervical or upper thoracic spine level. Less common sites include the thoracolumbar junction, conus medullaris, craniocervical junction, and sacral spine [2,5].

Only 2 cases of resection of bronchogenic cyst of the Filum Terminale have been described [3,5]. Nevertheless, the possibility of the existence of this pathology must be taken into account when conducting a differential diagnosis of intradural extramedullary neoplasm.

Microsurgical resection of symptomatic intraspinal bronchogenic cysts is necessary to acquire tissue for a conclusive histological diagnosis and to decompress neuronal components. Gross total resection should be attempted as it is associated with a significantly higher rate of symptomatic relief and a lower rate of recurrence than partial resection (82% vs. 18% and 0% vs. 63%, respectively). However, gross total resection could be achieved in only 48%, while subtotal or partial resection in the remaining 52% [1, 5]. Complete resection is often challenging due to the cyst's ventral location or adherence to critical neural structures, emphasizing the importance of electrophysiological monitoring during surgery [5].

Conclusions

Intraspinal bronchogenic cysts are a rare developmental anomaly. They are benign, characterized by slow growth and may remain asymptomatic. In symptomatic cases, the clinical presentation is variable, depending on location and similar to other lesions in the same location. For differential diagnosis of intradural extramedullary lesions, it is necessary to consider the possibility of the presence of a bronchogenic cyst.

The primary treatment for symptomatic cases is surgical resection. Complete resection eliminates the possibility of recurrence. However, complete resection may be difficult due to the risk of damage to adjacent structures. To minimize probable complication, we recommend using intraoperative ultrasound. We describe a case of complete resection of bronchogenic cyst of the Filum Terminale using ultrasound monitoring during surgery.

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